

Classification of viral proteins expressed by the SARS-CoV-2 genome

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Summary

Severe acute respiratory coronavirus 2 syndrome leads to Covid 19 disease, and spread rapidly worldwide in a pandemic mode. In order to control or avoid SARS-CoV-2 infection, it is essential to develop successful preventive or therapeutic strategies against the virus. For this reason, it is of great importance to understate the structure and function of the proteins, as well as the genome of SARS-CoV 2. The SARS-CoV-2 genome is remarkably similar to the coronavirus causing SARS in 2003, and much of the knowledge obtained for SARS-CoV-2 proteins is based on the various research studies published on SARS-CoV and other related viruses. The SARS-CoV-2 ge-

nome, similar to other coronaviruses, encodes four structural proteins (S, E, M, and N). This virus, moreover, expresses nine accessory proteins and 16 non-structural proteins. This review article provides a comprehensive insight into the SARS-CoV-2 genome and the structure and function of proteins. In addition, amino acid sequence alignment between SARS-CoV-2 and SARS-CoV is presented in this article.

Key words

SARS-CoV-2, COVID-19, CoVs Proteins, Open Reading Frames, Genome Structure

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Introduction

The novel SARS-CoV-2 coronavirus was recognised as a cause of acute respiratory disease that originally emerged in China in late 2019.¹ The World Health Organization (WHO) declared, in March 2020 and subsequent to the viral rapid spread worldwide, the situation as a pandemic.² SARS-CoV-2 has caused major human mortality and created significant public health concerns throughout the world.³ Phylogenetic studies of the entire genome and individual genes of SARS-CoV-2 have shown that SARS-CoV-2 closely resembles SARS-like bat coronaviruses belonging to the *Beta-coronavirus* genus class of the *Coronaviridae* family.⁴

The SARS-CoV-2 genome is a single strand, positive-sense RNA virus consisting of 29903 bases and encoding 29 structural and non-structural proteins (Table 1).^{5,6} The SARS-CoV-2 genome sequence is presented in the NCBI genome database (NC 045512.2); 11 protein-coding genes and 38 percent GC content are included in the genome.⁷

Five key open reading frames (ORFs), including ORF1ab (5' frameshifted polyprotein) and four major structural proteins, such as ORF2 (Spike protein), ORF4 (Envelope protein), ORF5 (Membrane protein), and ORF9 (Nucleocapsid protein), are expressed in the SARS-CoV-2. Accordingly, the genes of all coronaviruses have major structural proteins in the 5'–3' order:

S, E, M, and N.⁸ Nine accessory genes were found among or even overlapping the structural genes, namely ORF3a, ORF3d, ORF6, ORF7a, ORF7b, ORF8, ORF9b, ORF10, and ORF14.⁹

ORF1ab is located near the 5'-terminus of the SARS-CoV-2 genome and encodes pp1ab. Structural proteins, accessory proteins, and a part of an ORF1ab are situated at the 3'-terminus of the viral genome.¹⁰ Hence, this article summarizes the genomic and proteomic information of SARS-CoV-2, which is essential for designing a vaccine or therapeutic strategies against the newly emerged SARS-CoV-2 virus.

Structural proteins of SARS-CoV-2

SARS-CoV-2 has four structural proteins: the envelope (E), membrane (M), nucleocapsid (N), and spike (S) proteins, which are essential for viral assembly and function, as indicated above.⁸ The viral envelope is formed by the E and M proteins, and the N protein binds to the RNA genome of the virus, and the S protein binds to human receptors.¹¹ All the proteins and genome information of SARS-CoV-2 structural proteins are presented in table 2.

Spike protein (S) is a glycoprotein found on the surface of the virus, giving the virus a crown-like appearance.¹² The virus particle could reach the host cell

Table 1 SARS-CoV-2 consists of four structural proteins and nine accessory proteins, and 16 non-structural proteins.

Structural Proteins (4)	Accessory Proteins (6)	Nonstructural Proteins (16)
S (ORF2)	ORF3a	Nsp1
E (ORF4)	ORF3d	Nsp2
M (ORF5)	ORF6	Nsp3
N (ORF9)	ORF7a	Nsp4
	ORF7b	Nsp5
	ORF8	Nsp6
	ORF9b	Nsp7
	ORF10	Nsp8
	ORF14	Nsp9
		Nsp10
		Nsp11
		Nsp12
		Nsp13
		Nsp14
		Nsp15
		Nsp16

Figure 1 Schematic genome structure and protein classification of SARS-CoV-2.

with a glycoprotein spike attachment.¹³ The spike (S) protein consists of S1 and S2; the host ACE2 receptor

is recognized and bound by the S1 subunit, and the virus-cell fusion mechanism is mediated by the S2

Table 2 SARS-CoV-2 structural genomic and proteins information (Accession: NC_045512.2).

Gene symbol	Protein product name	CDS start Coordinates (5'..3')	CDS End	Gene Length (nt)	Protein Length (aa)	Mass (Da)	Molecular Function
S	Spike surface glycoprotein (ORF2)	21563	25384	3822	1273	141,178	receptor recognition and binding to human receptors
E	envelope protein (ORF4)	26245	26472	228	75	8,365	Envelope formation, virus morphogenesis, and assembly
M	membrane glycoprotein (ORF5)	26523	27191	669	222	25,147	Component of the viral envelope
N	nucleocapsid phosphoprotein (ORF9)	28274	29533	1260	419	45,626	binding, compacting, and packaging the viral genome

subunit.¹⁴ The protein size of S is between 180-200 kDa, which includes an extracellular N-terminus, a viral membrane-anchored transmembrane (TM) domain, and a short C-terminal intracellular segment (Figure 11).¹⁵ The total protein length of S protein is 1273 amino acids, which is the highest structural protein length among SARS-CoV-2 proteins and has a length of 3822 nt for this coding gene. This protein has proven a suitable target for producing vaccines, antibody therapies, and tests based on diagnostic antigens.^{16,17} The binding of SARS-CoV-2 spike to the human ACE2 receptors is approximately 10 to 20-fold higher than similar viruses, accounting for the easier human-to-human transmission.² The amino acid sequence alignment of SARS CoV-2 and SARS CoV spike protein is displayed in figure 2. Among all the structural proteins, spike protein has the most remarkable sequence divergence (75.881% identity with SARS-CoV).

Envelope protein (E) is a short, integral membrane protein made up of 75 amino acids existing in monomeric and homo-pentameric form and consisting of 40 loops and 35 alpha-helices.¹⁸ The E protein consists of three different domains, including the a short and hydrophilic N-terminus domain,, a hydrophobic transmembrane domain, and a long and hydrophilic c-ter-

минаl domain.¹⁹ The E protein is located along the S protein, and plays a vital role in the viral genome assembly, envelope formation, assembly and budding, and pathogenesis.²⁰ This protein is proposed to play a role as a viroporin, exhibiting an ion transport channel function. Ion channels have been long considered excellent candidates as therapeutic targets.²¹ E protein shows the highest sequence similarity (94.737%) between SARS CoV-2 and SARS CoV among the structural proteins (Figure 3). Amino acid residues Phenylalanine in position 56 is changed to Valine with a hydrophobic feature. In addition, SARS CoV-2 positive charged arginine is replaced in position 69 by negative charged glutamine.

Membrane glycoprotein (M) is a glycosylated structure that forms a single 3-transmembrane domain (TM), namely the N hydrophilic end of the membrane, the transmembrane domain, and the cytoplasmic domain.²² The M protein glycosylation forms the interaction between the virus and the host. The assembly of the virus is due to this highly conserved protein.²³ The amino acid sequence alignment for Membrane glycoprotein for SARS CoV-2 and SARS CoV shows 89.189 percent similarity (Figure 4).

Nucleocapsid phosphoprotein (N) in SARS-CoV-2

Figure 11

Structure of the SARS-CoV-2 structural proteins. a. Envelope protein b. Membrane protein c. Nucleocapsid phosphoprotein d. Spike protein Schematic representation of the SARS-CoV-2 spike.

P0DTC4 VEMP_SARS-CoV-2	MYSFVSEETGLIVNSVLLFLAFVVFLLVTLAILTALRLCAYCCNIVNLSLVKPSFYVYS	60
P59637 VEMP_SARS-CoV	MYSFVSEETGLIVNSVLLFLAFVVFLLVTLAILTALRLCAYCCNIVNLSLVKPTVYVYS	60
	*****.*****	
P0DTC4 VEMP_SARS-CoV-2	RVKNLNSSR-VPDLLV	75
P59637 VEMP_SARS-CoV	RVKNLNSSEGVPDLLV	76
	*****.*****	

Figure 3 **Envelope:** the amino acid sequence alignment of Envelope proteins from SARS-CoV-2 (P0DTC4) and SARS-CoV (P59637). (94.737% identity)

P0DTC5 VME1_SARS-CoV-2	MADSNGTITVEELKLLLEQWNLVIGFLFTWICLLQFAYANRNRFLYIIKLIFLWLLWPV	60
P59596 VME1_SARS-CoV	-MADNGTITVEELKQLLEQWNLVIGFLFLAWIMLLQFAYSNRNRFLYIIKLVFLWLLWPV	59
	.*****.*****.*****.*****.*****	
P0DTC5 VME1_SARS-CoV-2	TLACFVLAAYRINWITGGIAIAMACLVGLMWLSYFIASFRLFARTRSMWSFNPETNILL	120
P59596 VME1_SARS-CoV	TLACFVLAAYRINWVTGGIAIAMACIVGLMWLSYFVASFRLFARTRSMWSFNPETNILL	119
	*****.*****.*****.*****.*****.*****	
P0DTC5 VME1_SARS-CoV-2	NVPLHGTILTRPLLESELVIGAVILRGHLRIAGHHLGRCDIKDLPKEITVATSRTLSTYYK	180
P59596 VME1_SARS-CoV	NVPLRGTIVTRPLMESELVIGAVIIRGHLRMAGHSLGRCDIKDLPKEITVATSRTLSTYYK	179
	****.***.***.*****.*****.*** *****.*****	
P0DTC5 VME1_SARS-CoV-2	LGASQRVAGDSGFAAYSRYRIGNYKLNTDHSSSDNIALLVQ	222
P59596 VME1_SARS-CoV	LGASQRVGTDSGFAAYNRYRIGNYKLNTDHAGSNDNIALLVQ	221
	*****.*****.*****.*****.*****.*****	

Figure 4 **Membrane glycoprotein:** the amino acid sequence alignment of Membrane glycoprotein from SARS-CoV-2 (P0DTC5) and SARS-CoV (P59596). (89.189% identity)

binds to the RNA virus genome to help RNA packaging and virions assembly.²⁴ The RNA-binding N protein comprises an N-terminal domain (NTD) that captures RNA genome and mediates interaction with the virus genome (RNA binding domain). The C-terminal domain (CTD) forms a compact dimer that has been proposed to anchor the ribonucleoprotein complex to the viral membrane via its interaction with the Membrane protein (dimerization domains).^{25,26} The protein sequence alignment for Nucleocapsid phosphoprotein for SARS CoV-2 and SARS-CoV is presented in figure 5 with 89.1% identity.

Accessory Proteins of SARS-CoV-2:

SARS-CoV-2 contains multiple open reading frames (ORFs) that encode nine accessory proteins, namely ORFs 3a, 3d, 6, 7a, 7b, 8, 9b, 10, and 14 (table3). The accessory proteins vary in position, number, and size in different coronaviruses subgroups. These proteins are also responsible for virus spreading and pathogenicity.^{27,28} In various groups of coronaviruses, the accessory genes show heterogeneity and no similarity in gene sequence with other viral proteins.²⁹ Among

past human coronaviruses, SARS-CoV (Severe acute respiratory syndrome-related coronavirus) is the nearest to SARS-CoV-2. SARS-CoV genome contains 9 accessory proteins including 3a, 3b, 6, 7a, 7b, 8a, 8b, 9b and 9c.^{30,31}

ORF3a is the largest accessory protein in SARS-CoV-2 that plays a vital role in pathogenesis, containing 275 amino acids and approximately 31 kDa of molecular weight.^{31,32} ORF3a protein is the ion channel (viroporin) protein that localizes to the cell surface and modulates virus release from the host cells. ORF3a is indispensable for virus replication and pathogenesis.³³ It is also proposed that an association exists between an ORF3a mutation and a higher risk of infection and mortality.³² A striking similarity predicts functional conservation between ORF3a in SARS-CoV-2 and SARS-CoV (Figure 6).

ORF6, with 61 amino acids and approximately 7 kDa, is a small accessory protein in SARS-CoV-2. The function of this protein is not fully understood in SARS-CoV-2, but ORF6 of SARS-CoV-2 has a 69 percent identity of the amino acid sequence with SARS-CoV (Figure 7).^{34,35} In SARS-CoV, ORF6 is an effective antagonist of interferon type I (IFN) production and signaling.^{36,37}

P0DTC9 NCAP_SARS-CoV-2	MSDNGPQ-NQRNAPRITFGGSPDSTGSNQNGERSGARSKQRRPQGLPNNTASWFTALTQH	59
P59595 NCAP_SARS-CoV	MSDNGPQSNQRSAPRITFGGPTDSTDNQNGRNGARPKQRRPQGLPNNTASWFTALTQH	60
***** ** .*****:***.*** ** * ** *****		
P0DTC9 NCAP_SARS-CoV-2	GKEDLKFRPQQGVPINTNSPDDQIGYRRATRIRGGDGKMKDLSRWYFYLLGTGPEA	119
P59595 NCAP_SARS-CoV	GKEELRFPRQQGVPINTNSPDDQIGYRRATRIRGGDGKMKELSPRWYFYLLGTGPEA	120
.*:***.*****.*****.*****		
P0DTC9 NCAP_SARS-CoV-2	GLPYGANKDGIWVATEGALNTPKDHIGTRNPANNAIIVLQLPQGTTLPKGFYAEGSRGG	179
P59595 NCAP_SARS-CoV	SLPYGANKEGIVWATEGALNTPKDHIGTRNPNNAAATVLLPQGTTLPKGFYAEGSRGG	180
.*****:**.***** ** * *****		
P0DTC9 NCAP_SARS-CoV-2	SQASSRSSSRNRNSTPGSSRGTSARMAGNGGDAALALLLDRLNQLKESKMSGKQ	239
P59595 NCAP_SARS-CoV	SQASSRSSSRNRNSTPGSSRGNSPARMASGGGETALALLLDRLNQLKESKMSGKQ	240
*****.*****.*****.***:*****:*****		
P0DTC9 NCAP_SARS-CoV-2	QQQGQTVTKKSAEASKKPRQKRTATKAYNVTQAFGRRGPEQTQGNFGDQELIRQGTDYK	299
P59595 NCAP_SARS-CoV	QQQGQTVTKKSAEASKKPRQKRTATKQYNVTQAFGRRGPEQTQGNFGDQDLIRQGTDYK	300
***** *****.*****		
P0DTC9 NCAP_SARS-CoV-2	HWPQIAQFAPSASAFFGMSRIGMEVTPSGTWLTYGAIKLDKDPNFKDQVILLNKHIDA	359
P59595 NCAP_SARS-CoV	HWPQIAQFAPSASAFFGMSRIGMEVTPSGTWLTYGAIKLDKDPQFKDNVILLNKHIDA	360
***** *****:***:*****		
P0DTC9 NCAP_SARS-CoV-2	YKTFPPEPKKDKKKKADEQALPQRQKKQPTVTLPAADLDDFSKQLQSSMSADSTQA	419
P59595 NCAP_SARS-CoV	YKTFPPEPKKDKKKKDEAQLPQRQKKQPTVTLPAADMDDFSRQLQNSMSGASADST	420
*****:**.* ***** *****:***:***:***.*.: .:		
P0DTC9 NCAP_SARS-CoV-2	--	
P59595 NCAP_SARS-CoV	QA	422

Figure 5 Nucleocapsid phosphoprotein: The amino acid sequence alignment of Nucleocapsid phosphoprotein from SARS-CoV-2 (P0DTC9) and SARS-CoV (P59595). (89.1% identity)

Figure 6 ORF3a: The amino acid sequence alignment of ORF3a from SARS-CoV-2 (P0DTC3) and SARS-CoV (P59632). (72.727% identity)

Figure 7 ORF6: The amino acid sequence alignment of ORF6 from SARS-CoV-2 (P0DTC6) and SARS-CoV (P59634). (66.667% identity)

ORF7a is the second-largest accessory protein, encoding 121 amino acids located in the 3' region of the SARS-CoV-2 genome. Little is known about its function. ORF7a is composed of type I transmembrane protein with a crystal structure.^{38,39} Bioinformatics analysis displayed that ORF7a could play a role in suppressing the antivirus host response.⁴⁰ The sequence alignment for ORF7a protein for SARS CoV-2 and SARS CoV is shown in Figure 8.

ORF7b protein is a putative viral accessory protein with just 43 amino acids and 5,180 Da molecular weight that localizes to the Golgi apparatus.³⁰ This highly hydrophobic protein contains a transmembrane helical domain (TMD) necessary for Golgi complex localization (figure 12). Moreover, this protein's

highly hydrophobic nature suggests that ORF7b is a transmembrane protein.^{41,42} The amino acid sequence alignment for ORF7b for SARS CoV-2 and SARS CoV exhibits 79.545% similarity (Figure 9).

ORF8 is a 121-amino acid protein, ORF8 chain, and a hydrophobic signal peptide.⁴³ ORF8 has numerous functions, including inhibition of interferon 1 signaling by adding the interferon regulatory factor 3 (IRF3) region to the IRF association domain (IAD), viral replication, inducing apoptosis, and modulating/inducing pathways of cell stress.^{9,29,44} Figure 10 depicts the sequence alignment of ORF8 protein for SARS-CoV-2 and SARS-CoV ORF8a and ORF8b. It is clear that ORF8 SARS CoV-2 has less similarity with ORF8a and ORF8b SARS CoV compared to other accessory proteins.

P0DTC7 NS7A_SARS-CoV-2	MKIILFLALITLATCELYHYQECVRGTTVLLKEPCSSGTYEGNSPFHPLADNKFALTCFS	60
P59635 NS7A_SARS-CoV	MKIILFLTLIVFTSCELYHYQECVRGTTVLLKEPCPSGTYEGNSPFHPLADNKFALTCTS	60
	*****:*:*:::*****	
P0DTC7 NS7A_SARS-CoV-2	TQFAFACPDGVKHYVQLRARSVSPKLFIRQEEV-QELYSPIFLIVAIVFITLCFTLKRK	119
P59635 NS7A_SARS-CoV	THFAFACADGTRHTYQLRARSVSPKLFIRQEEVQELYSPLFLIVAALVFLILCFTIKRK	120
	*:***** **:*_* ***** *****:*****:*:* ***:***	
P0DTC7 NS7A_SARS-CoV-2	TE	121
P59635 NS7A_SARS-CoV	TE	122
	**	

Figure 8 ORF7a: The amino acid sequence alignment of ORF7a from SARS-CoV-2 (P0DTC7) and SARS-CoV (P596345). (66.667% identity)

P0DTD8 NS7B_SARS-CoV-2	MIELSLIDFYLCFLAFLFLVLIMLIIFWFSLELQDHNETCHA-	43
Q7TFA1 NS7B_SARS-CoV	MNELTLIDFYLCFLAFLFLVLIMLIIFWFSLEIQDLEEPCTKV	44
	*****:*****:*:*	

Figure 9 ORF7b: The amino acid sequence alignment of ORF7b from SARS-CoV-2 (P0DTD8) and SARS-CoV (Q7TFA1). (79.545% identity)

Figure 12
Structure of the SARS-CoV-2 accessory proteins.

Q80H93 NS8B_SARS-CoV	MCLKILVRYNT-----RGNTYSTAWLCALGK-----	26
P0DTC8 NS8_SARS-CoV-2	--MKFLVFLGIITTVAAAFHQECSLQSQCTQHQPYYVDDPCPIHFYSKWYIRVGARKSAPLI	58
Q7TFA0 NS8A_SARS-CoV	--MKLLIVL-----TC-----	9
	:*:~*:	
Q80H93 NS8B_SARS-CoV	-----VLP--FHRWHTMVQCTPNVTINCQDPAGGALIARCWYLHEGHQTAAFRDV	75
P0DTC8 NS8_SARS-CoV-2	ELCVDEAGSKSPIQYIDIGNYTVSCL-PFTINCQEPKLGSLVVRCSFYEDFLEYHDVRRVV	117
Q7TFA0 NS8A_SARS-CoV	-----ISL--CSCICTVVQRCASNKPHVLED-----PCKVQH-----	39
	. . * :: * .	
Q80H93 NS8B_SARS-CoV	LVVLNKR TN 84	
P0DTC8 NS8_SARS-CoV-2	LDFI----- 121	
Q7TFA0 NS8A_SARS-CoV	-----	

Figure 10 ORF8: The amino acid sequence alignment of ORF8 from SARS-CoV-2 (P0DTC8) and SARS-CoV (Q7TFA0) ORF8a (9.91% identity) and SARS-CoV (Q80h93) ORF8b (14.961% identity).

ORF10 has 38 amino acids located upstream of the 3'-UTR. The ORF10 expresses a small protein that is the smallest protein among the accessory proteins of SARS-CoV-2, and its function is unknown in SARS-CoV-2. This protein has no resemblance to other recognized proteins in sequence and function.⁴⁵ According to secondary structure prediction, the ORF10 protein, consisting of one alpha-helix and two beta-strands, has a hydrophobic nature.^{45,46}

Non-structural proteins (Nsp) of SARS-CoV-2:

The first gene (ORF1ab) expresses a polyprotein with 7,096 amino acids and 794,058 Da molecular weight (Table 4).⁴⁷ The ORF1ab polyprotein is comprised of 16 non-structural proteins (NSPs).⁴⁸ The non-structural proteins of SARS-CoV-2 express two huge polyproteins that further cleaved proteolytically to produce 16 smaller proteins, making them highly promising drug targets.⁴⁹ After the virus reaches the cell, the virus RNA transcript expresses non-structural proteins (Nsp1...16) with the use of two open reading frames (ORF1a and ORF1b) (table4).⁴⁹ ORF1a/b is approximately two-thirds of the total length of the genome that encodes 16 NSPs (Figure 13). ORF1a and ORF1b contain a frameshift in between, which produces two polypeptides: pp1a and pp1ab.⁸ Subsequently, these two polypeptides are processed by two cysteine proteases (one a papain-like, PL-PRO), and then 16 non-structural proteins (NSPs) are made.⁵⁰ The amino acid sequence alignment of Replicase polyprotein 1ab from SARS-CoV-2 (P0DTC8) and SARS-CoV (P0C6X7) exhibits 86.125% identity.

Nsp1 (leader protein) is the first polyprotein known as the leader protein and encodes via the gene near

the 5' end of the viral genome.⁵¹ This protein has a significant role in pathogenesis by binding to the 40S ribosomal subunit of the host cell to inactivate mRNA translation and promotes host mRNA degradation upon infection.⁵² The nsp1-40s ribosome complex is responsible for cleaving the host cell mRNAs adjacent to the 5' UTR region and promotes their degradation. Due to the leader sequence located in the 5' UTR site, the viral mRNAs are not susceptible to cleavage and evade degradation. By inhibiting the host gene expression, nsp1 promotes viral gene expression in virus-infected cells and evades the host immune system.⁵³

Nsp2 protein is indispensable for modulating the signaling process of host cell survival by binding to two host proteins: prohibitin1 and prohibitin2 (PHB1 and PHB2).⁵⁴ PHB1 and PHB2 proteins demonstrate different cellular localization such as mitochondria, cytosol, and nucleus responsible for various cell function functions, including cell cycle progression, cell migration, cellular differentiation, apoptosis, and mitochondrial biogenesis. The binding of NSP2 to proteins PHB1 and PHB2 underlines the role of NSP2 in disturbing the host cell environment.⁵⁵

Nsp3 (Papain-like proteinase) is the papain-like proteinase with a transmembrane domain.⁵⁶ This protein is responsible for cleavage at the N-terminus of the replicase polyprotein. It is divided in the site between NSP2 and NSP3, releasing NSP1, NSP2, and NSP3 from the coronavirus N-terminal region of polyproteins 1a and 1ab.^{57,58}

Nsp4 is a membrane-spanning protein with 500 amino acids. This protein participates in membrane rearrangement by interacting with NSP3 and other host proteins, which is indispensable for virus replication.⁵⁹ The alpha-helix domain of this protein is involved in the protein-protein interaction that binds to

Table 3 SARS-CoV-2 accessory protein information (Accession: NC_045512.2).

Protein name	Gene symbol	CDS start Coordinates (5'..3')	CDS End	CDS Length (nt)	Protein Length (aa)	Mass (Da)	Function
ORF3a Protein	ORF3a	25393	26220	828	275	31,123	Form potassium ion channels (viroporin)
ORF6 protein	ORF6	27202	27387	186	61	7,273	antagonist of type I interferon (IFN) signaling
ORF7a protein	ORF7a	27394	27759	366	121	13,744	Host response suppression (theoretically)
ORF7b protein	ORF7b	27756	27887	132	43	5,180	viral replication/ inhibition of interferon 1
ORF8 protein	ORF8	27894	28259	366	121	13,831	host-virus interaction
ORF10 Protein	ORF10	29558	29674	117	38	4,449	Unknown

the replicase-transcriptase complex of the virus, which is essential for the replication process.⁴⁸

Nsp5 (3C-Like Proteinase) with protease activity plays an important role in the SARS-CoV-2 replication process. Nsp5 cleaves the C-terminus region of replicase polyprotein at 11 specific sites to make Nsp4-Nsp16 insensible in different replicating and transcribing techniques.⁴⁸

Nsp6 has 290 amino acids that bind to the host endoplasmic reticulum (ER) sigma receptor to generate autophagosomes. Sigma receptor activation facilitates the assembly of replicase proteins and regulates stress response.⁶⁰

Nsp7 and Nsp8 are peptides with 83 and 198 amino acids, respectively. The attachment between the NSP7 and NSP8 (peptide cofactor) forms a hexadecamer known as primase complex. NSP7 and NSP8 heterodimer interacts with RNA-dependent RNA polymerase (Nsp12), including RNA polymerase responsible for viral RNA synthesis and replication.^{61,62}

Nsp9 is a single-stranded RNA-binding protein that promotes viral replication.⁶³

Nsp10 as a cofactor is responsible for stimulating

Nsp14 (guanine-N7 methyltransferase) and Nsp16 (2'-O-ribose methyltransferase) activity. Furthermore, Nsp10 plays a pivotal role in the methylation of mRNAs guanosine cap, which is essential for viral transcription and nuclear export of viral mRNA. Nsp10-Nsp14-Nsp16 are theoretically suitable candidates for antiviral drug development.⁶⁴

Nsp11 consists of 13 amino acids, the smallest non-structural protein peptides in SARS CoV-2. The function of this protein is not fully understood.⁶⁵

Nsp12 (RNA-Dependent RNA Polymerase) (RdRp) consists of 932 amino acids with the polymerase domain. The amino acid sequence displays approximately 96% identity to SARS Nsp12.⁶⁶ RdRp is insensible in replicating and transcribing the viral RNA genome of SARS-CoV-2. As mentioned before, the interaction between Nsp12 and primase complex (Nsp7/Nsp8) shapes RNA synthesis that is essential in prolonged RNA replication.⁶⁷

Nsp13 (Helicase) is a multifunctional protein, a zinc-binding domain in N-terminus, responsible for RNA duplex-unwinding activity in a 5' to 3' direction. Furthermore, Nsp13 has helicase activity depending

Table 4 SARS-CoV-2 non-structural proteins genomic information (GeneBank Accession: MN908947).

Protein name	Gene symbol	CDS start Coordinates (5'..3')	CDS End	CDS Length (nt)	Protein Length (aa)	Function
Nsp1 (leader protein)	ORF1ab	266	805	540	180	Inhibits host mRNA translation by interacting with the 40S ribosomal subunit.
Nsp2	ORF1ab	806	2719	1914	638	host cell survival signaling pathway
Nsp3	ORF1ab	2720	8554	5835	1945	Responsible for the cleavages located at the N-terminus of the replicase polyprotein to generate Nsp1, Nsp2 and Nsp3
Nsp4	ORF1ab	8555	10054	1500	500	Interacts with Nsp3 and promotes viral replication
Nsp5 (3C-Like Proteinase)	ORF1ab	10055	10972	918	306	Proteolytic cleavage of C-terminus of the replicase poly protein
Nsp6	ORF1ab	10973	11842	870	290	Induces autophagosomes
Nsp7	ORF1ab	11843	12091	249	83	Viral genome transcription and replication
Nsp8	ORF1ab	12092	12685	594	198	Viral genome transcription and replication
Nsp9	ORF1ab	12686	13024	339	113	viral replication by binding to viral genome ssRNA
Nsp10	ORF1ab	13025	13441	417	139	viral mRNAs cap methylation
Nsp11	ORF1ab	13442	13480	39	13	Viral genome transcription and replication
Nsp12 (RNA-Dependent RNA Polymerase)	ORF1ab	13442	16237	2796	932	replication and transcription of the viral RNA genome
Nsp13 (Helicase)	ORF1ab	16238	18040	1803	601	Unwinds duplex RNA
Nsp14) (3' To-5' Exonuclease)	ORF1ab	18041	19621	1581	527	Acts as a proofreading exoribonuclease for RNA replication
Nsp15 (EndoRNase)	ORF1ab	19622	20659	1038	346	Prevents vural recognition from the host immune system
Nsp16 (2'-O-Ribose Methyl-transferase)	ORF1ab	20660	21553	894	298	viral mRNAs cap methylation which is essential to evade immune system

on Mn²⁺ (magnesium).⁶⁸ In the replication of SARS-CoV-2, the helicase and NTPase activities of Nsp13 play a pivotal role, making it a suitable candidate for antiviral target.⁶⁹

Nsp14 (3'-To-5' Exonuclease) has two distinct activities: 3'-5' exoribonuclease activity (proofreading) that acts on single-stranded RNA and double-stranded RNA N7-guanine methyltransferase activity at the C-terminus of the SARS-CoV-2 genome. Moreover, the interaction of Nsp14 with Nsp10 and Nsp16 is essential for RNA synthesis.⁷⁰

Nsp15 (EndoRNase) is an Mn²⁺-dependent protein with endoribonuclease activity that forms 2'-3'-cyclic phosphatases by cleaving uridylates at the 3'-position of RNA. Nsp15 performs various essential roles, such as interferon (IFN) antagonism, while also preventing the virus from being recognized by the host immune system by degrading the polyuridine sequence.⁷¹

Nsp16 (2'-O-Ribose Methyltransferase). The SARS-CoV-2 viral RNA contains a 5'-cap structure essential for the virus from degradation by 5'-exoribonucleases and critical for evading the virus from the immune system.⁷²

Conclusion and future perspective:

The widespread outbreak of the COVID-19 pandemic requires numerous studies related to the genes and proteins of the SARS-CoV2. Advances in the genome, protein structure, and function knowledge enable researchers to design suitable vaccines that inhibit the virus and develop effective treatment strategies. For this reason, the genome structure and protein function are reviewed and discussed herein. When evaluating SARS-CoV and SARS-CoV-2 genomes, despite some sequence variation, SARS-CoV-2 and SARS-CoV's primary amino acid sequence displays striking similarity.

Abbreviations:

NTD: N-terminal domain, **SARS CoV-2:** severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2, **ACE2:** angiotensin-converting enzyme 2, **IFN:** interferon, **RdRp:** RNA-Dependent RNA Polymerase, **ER:** endoplasmic reticulum, **NSPs:** non-structural proteins, **IRF3:** interferon regulatory factor 3, **CTD:** C-terminal domain, **ORF:** Open Reading Frame, **TM:** transmembrane

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Figure 13 Structure prediction and structure-based function annotation of SARS-CoV-2 non-structural proteins.

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Περίληψη

Classification of viral proteins expressed by the SARS-CoV-2 genome

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Το σοβαρό οξύ αναπνευστικό σύνδρομο οφειλόμενο σε λοίμωξη από τον κορωνοϊό SARS-CoV-2, οδηγεί στη νόσο COVID 19, η οποία εξαπλώθηκε με ταχείς ρυθμούς παγκοσμίως σε πανδημική μορφή. Για τον έλεγχο ή την αποφυγή της μόλυνσης από τον ιό SARS-CoV-2, είναι απαραίτητο να βρεθούν επιτυχημένες προληπτικές ή θεραπευτικές στρατηγικές κατά του ιού. Για το λόγο αυτό, είναι πολύ σημαντική η κατανόηση της δομής και της λειτουργίας των πρωτεϊνών, καθώς και του γονιδιώματος του SARS-CoV 2 με στόχο την εύρεση επιτυχημένης θεραπευτικής προσέγγισης κατά του νεοεμφανιζόμενου ιού. Το γονιδίωμα του SARS-CoV-2 είναι αξιοσημείωτα παρόμοιο με τον κορωνοϊό που προκάλεσε τη νόσο SARS το 2003 και μεγάλο μέρος της γνώσης που αποκτήθηκε για τις πρωτεΐνες SARS-CoV-2 βασίζεται στις διάφορες ερευνητικές μελέτες που δημοσιεύθηκαν για τον SARS-CoV και άλλους, σχετικούς ιούς. Το γονιδίωμα SARS-CoV-2, παρόμοιο με άλλους κορωνοϊούς, κωδικοποιεί τέσσερις δομικές πρωτεΐνες (S, E, M και N). Αυτός ο ιός, επιπλέον, εκφράζει εννέα βοηθητικές πρωτεΐνες και 16 μη δομικές πρωτεΐνες. Στο παρόν άρθρο ανασκόπησης παρέχεται μια ολοκληρωμένη εικόνα για το γονιδίωμα του SARS-CoV-2, καθώς και τη δομή και τη λειτουργία των πρωτεϊνών του. Επιπρόσθετα, παρουσιάζονται οι ομοιότητες της αλληλουχίας των αμινοξέων μεταξύ των ιών SARS-CoV-2 και SARS-CoV.

Λέξεις κλειδιά

SARS-CoV-2, COVID-19, πρωτεΐνες CoVs, ανοικτά πλαίσια ανάγνωσης, δομή γονιδιώματος

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